

The Effectiveness of Workplace Inclusion Programs on ASN Productivity: The Mediating Role of Organizational Commitment

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the effectiveness of workplace inclusion programs in increasing the productivity of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) in Ponorogo Regency, and examines the role of organizational commitment as a mediating variable. Using a quantitative explanatory approach and Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) analysis technique, this study involved 99 ASN selected through a purposive sampling method. The results showed that the inclusion program had a positive and highly significant effect on organizational commitment ($\beta = 0.771$; $p < 0.001$), and a direct effect on ASN productivity ($\beta = 0.352$; $p < 0.01$). Organizational commitment was also shown to have a significant effect on productivity ($\beta = 0.357$; $p < 0.01$). The mediating effect of organizational commitment was declared significant ($\beta = 0.276$; $p = 0.011$). The research model demonstrated a good fit, with an SRMR value of 0.045 and an R-square value of 0.594 for organizational commitment and 0.446 for ASN productivity. These findings confirm that the inclusion program is not merely an ethical policy, but an effective strategic managerial approach to improving community performance productivity by strengthening organizational commitment.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In today's era of globalization, workplace diversity and inclusion have become increasingly important issues in human resource management (HRM). Workplace diversity and inclusion have become a significant focus in human resource management (HRM) in recent decades. Organizations that create an inclusive work environment often enjoy various benefits, including increased employee creativity, innovation, and productivity. In Indonesia, particularly in the government sector, the importance of inclusion programs is increasingly relevant given the country's diversity, including ethnicity, religion, gender, and socioeconomic background. This diversity, when properly managed through inclusion programs, can be a significant source of strength for organizations, enhancing creativity, innovation, and overall performance (1).

Research conducted by (2) used Brewer's theory of optimal distinctiveness (3) to develop a definition of employee inclusion in workgroups that involves satisfying the needs for belonging and uniqueness. Based on this definition, the authors then presented an inclusion framework. Their framework was then used as a basis for reviewing the inclusion and diversity literature. Potential

contextual factors and outcomes associated with inclusion were suggested to guide future research.

Inclusion programs are designed to ensure that all employees feel valued, accepted, and able to contribute fully to the organization. Research shows that an inclusive work environment can increase employee motivation and engagement, which in turn positively impacts productivity (4). Furthermore, effective inclusion can reduce turnover and increase employee loyalty (5).

The success of an inclusion program depends not only on its implementation but also on how employees perceive and respond to the inclusive work environment. One key factor that can mediate the relationship between inclusion programs and productivity is organizational commitment. (6) Defines organizational commitment as an employee's desire to remain part of an organization, which consists of three components: affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment. Employees with high organizational commitment tend to be more productive and contribute more to organizational goals (6).

Workplace diversity refers to the existence of variations in individual characteristics within an organization, including but not limited to differences in gender, age, ethnicity,

religion, and educational background. Inclusion, on the other hand, is the effort to ensure that all individuals feel accepted, valued, and supported within the organization. Inclusion programs include various initiatives such as diversity awareness training, anti-discrimination policies, and the development of flexible work policies (7).

Several studies have shown that diversity and inclusion in the workplace can provide various benefits, including increased productivity, creativity, and job satisfaction (8). However, these benefits can only be achieved if diversity is accompanied by effective inclusion. In the context of civil servants (ASN), inclusion programs are crucial because ASN must be able to serve diverse communities fairly and effectively.

The Indonesian context, and particularly local governments, presents unique challenges: bureaucratic reform and human resource quality improvement are ongoing, but the implementation of inclusion policies has not always been systematically integrated at the operational level. Recent studies on HR development strategies in the current government significantly link bureaucratic reform, which encourages the digitalization of personnel management processes, improving civil servant competencies through digital-based training and performance systems, and efforts to strengthen the professionalism of officials (9). This calls for empirical studies linking diversity and inclusion policies to job satisfaction (10).

In Ponorogo Regency, civil servants (ASN) have a relatively high diversity in terms of age, educational level, and position. However, empirical evidence and internal evaluations reveal several gaps that require attention. First, inclusion policies have not been evenly distributed across regional government agencies (SKPD), resulting in limited representation and access to opportunities for some employee groups. Second, productivity outcomes across SKPDs show disparities, with SKPDs with inclusive practices tending to outperform those without. Third, there are indications of low organizational commitment among some ASN, for example, related to feelings of underappreciation, limited access to career development, and perceptions of unfairness in promotions, which have the potential to weaken the effectiveness of bureaucratic reform. These findings indicate a gap between desired inclusion policies and actual practice, necessitating a comprehensive study to examine the causal relationships and psychological mechanisms involved. (11) (Note: Local data and field observations underlie this gap formulation; this study aims to test this empirical relationship).

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of workplace inclusion programs on civil servant productivity in Ponorogo Regency. Furthermore, it explores the role of organizational commitment as a mediating variable in the relationship between inclusion programs and civil servant productivity. Therefore, this study is expected to provide deeper insights

into how inclusion programs can be effectively implemented to increase civil servant productivity and commitment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Job Demands-Resources Theory

Job Engagement Theory, or Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory, was developed by Arnold Bakker and Evangelia Demerouti in 2007 (12). Rooted in the job stress model and motivation theory, this theory offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how various aspects of work influence employee engagement, well-being, and performance. Furthermore, Job Engagement Theory (JD-R) explains how various aspects of work can influence employee engagement and work outcomes, such as productivity and well-being.

JD-R Theory groups job characteristics into two main categories: job demands and job resources.

1. Job Demands

Job demands are aspects of work that require sustained physical, psychological, social, or organizational effort. Examples include high workloads, time pressure, and role conflict. Job demands can lead to burnout and stress if not managed effectively.

2. Job Resources

Job resources are aspects of work that assist in achieving job goals, reduce job demands, and stimulate personal growth and development. Examples include social support from coworkers and superiors, autonomy, and development opportunities.

The relevance of this theory to this research lies in the fact that, from the perspective of job demands, the challenges faced by civil servants (ASN) in carrying out their daily tasks can be considered job demands. Inclusion programs can help mitigate these demands by creating a more supportive and inclusive work environment. Meanwhile, from the perspective of job resources, inclusion programs can be considered job resources that provide social support, skills development, and rewards to civil servants (ASN). These resources can increase civil servant engagement and ultimately impact their work productivity.

B. Workplace Inclusion Program

Workplace inclusion programs are a set of policies and practices aimed at creating a work environment that respects and accommodates individual differences, including differences in gender, race, age, disability, and socio-economic background (8).

A workplace inclusion program is a systematic effort by an organization to create a work environment that values and supports individual diversity. This program aims to ensure that every employee, regardless of their background, feels valued, supported, and given equal opportunities to contribute and grow (8). Inclusion

is more than just diversity; it ensures that diversity can fully contribute to the organization's goals. Inclusion programs are often associated with increased employee job satisfaction, loyalty, and productivity (7).

Research shows that workplace inclusion programs can provide various benefits to organizations. According to (2), an inclusive work environment can increase job satisfaction, employee loyalty, and overall organizational performance. Furthermore, (13) found that inclusion programs can increase creativity and innovation in organizations by leveraging diverse employee perspectives. Workplace inclusion programs are essential for creating a fair, supportive, and productive work environment. By implementing diversity awareness training, anti-discrimination policies, and flexible work policies, organizations can create an environment that supports diversity and maximizes employee potential.

According to (14) and (12), workplace inclusion programs involve various initiatives and practices aimed at creating an environment that values and supports individual diversity. The following are some relevant indicators often used to measure the effectiveness of workplace inclusion programs:

1. Anti-Discrimination Policies
2. Diversity Awareness Training
3. Flexible Work Policies
4. Representation in Decision-Making
5. Employee Satisfaction and Engagement
6. Evaluation and Feedback
7. Recognition and Awards

C. Work Productivity

Work productivity refers to the efficiency and effectiveness of employees in completing their tasks. Productivity can be influenced by various factors, including motivation, skills, and the work environment (15). Studies show that an inclusive work environment can increase productivity by creating a supportive work environment that values the contributions of each individual (16).

Work productivity is the comparison between the results achieved (output) with the total resources used or input (17) According to (18) work productivity is the comparison between what is produced with what is input. Work productivity is the ability to produce goods and services from a workforce, machine, or other production factors calculated based on the average time of the workforce in the production process. According to (19) what is meant by work productivity is a measure of production efficiency, namely a comparison between output results and input (output and input), input is often limited to labor input, while output is measured in physical units in the form of value.

Work productivity is one of the main indicators in assessing organizational performance, including

government organizations. Productivity refers to the efficiency and effectiveness of employees in completing tasks and achieving established goals. According to (15), productivity can be defined as the ratio between output produced and input used. In the context of ASN (State Civil Apparatus), productivity refers to the extent to which civil servants are able to provide optimal public services with available resources.

According to (20) productivity indicators include:

1. Competence

Capacity demonstrates an individual's capacity to perform work in accordance with assigned duties and responsibilities. This capability encompasses the knowledge, skills, and expertise an employee possesses to complete work accurately and precisely. Employees with good competencies will more easily understand their work, minimize errors, and be able to work independently without excessive supervision.

2. Improving results achieved.

This indicator illustrates the extent to which an individual is able to increase the quantity and quality of their work output. Work productivity is assessed based on an employee's ability to achieve work targets and demonstrate performance improvement over time. Improved results reflect the effectiveness of the individual's work and their commitment to contributing to the achievement of organizational goals.

3. Work Morale

Work morale relates to an individual's mental attitude, motivation, and enthusiasm in carrying out their work. Employees with high work morale demonstrate discipline, responsibility, and a willingness to work diligently. Good work morale encourages individuals to remain productive even when facing pressure or challenges at work.

4. Self-development

Self-development is an individual's effort to continuously improve their abilities and competencies. This can be achieved through training, education, and work experience. Employees who are aware of their self-development will be more adaptable to change and able to continuously improve the quality and productivity of their work.

5. Quality

Quality refers to the quality of work produced by an individual. Productivity is measured not only by the quantity of output, but also by the level of accuracy, neatness, and conformity of work results to established standards. High work quality reflects the professionalism and responsibility of employees in carrying out their duties.

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6. Efficiency

Efficiency relates to an individual's ability to optimally utilize resources, such as time, energy, and costs, to produce maximum work results. Efficient employees are able to complete work quickly and accurately without wasting resources, thus supporting increased overall work productivity.

D. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is the level of emotional and psychological attachment employees have to their organization. This commitment is often associated with positive outcomes such as better performance, lower absenteeism, and higher employee retention (21). Organizational commitment can also act as a mediator in the relationship between inclusion programs and employee productivity (12).

The organizational commitment of each employee reflects their job satisfaction with what the company has provided. Each employee's organizational commitment will certainly be different. (22) stated that organizational commitment is a state where an employee sides with the goals of the organization and has a desire to maintain their membership in the organization. (23) stated that organizational commitment is a strong desire for someone to maintain membership in an organization. Meanwhile (24) Job involvement is an important dimension of affective commitment, which reflects the extent to which employees feel involved and motivated by their work.

According to (25) the indicators that are often used to measure organizational commitment are as follows.

1. Job Involvement

Job involvement indicates the extent to which employees are psychologically engaged and actively participate in their work. Employees with high organizational commitment tend to demonstrate greater involvement, characterized by a willingness to devote energy, attention, and time to completing

tasks. High levels of job involvement reflect a sense of ownership in the work and the organization.

2. Absenteeism and Turnover Rates

Absenteeism and turnover rates are behavioral indicators that reflect employees' organizational commitment. Employees with high commitment tend to have lower absenteeism rates and a lower desire to leave the organization. Conversely, high absenteeism and turnover rates indicate a weak emotional and psychological bond between employees and the organization.

3. Employee Loyalty

Employee loyalty refers to an individual's willingness to remain with an organization and support its goals and values. Loyalty is reflected in employee commitment, willingness to defend the organization, and desire to make long-term contributions. According to (25), loyalty is a tangible manifestation of strong organizational commitment.

4. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction relates to the level of positive feelings employees have toward their jobs, the work environment, and the organization as a whole. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to have higher organizational commitment because they feel their needs and expectations are met. High job satisfaction encourages employees to remain with the organization and contribute optimally to it.

5. Employee Performance

Employee performance is the work results achieved by individuals in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. According to (25), high organizational commitment is positively related to increased employee performance. Employees with strong commitment will work more diligently, demonstrate a high level of responsibility, and strive to achieve organizational targets and goals.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

E. The Relationship between Workplace Inclusion Programs and Organizational Commitment

This is in line with research conducted by (26) which reviews five best practices for effective diversity

and inclusion efforts in the workplace. This research highlights that effective inclusion initiatives can increase employee engagement and organizational commitment. This article also emphasizes the importance of leadership

support in implementing successful inclusion programs (Harvard Business Review). Furthermore, a different study conducted by (27) illustrates how an organization's commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) can influence employee behavior. This study found that employees' positive perceptions of DEI programs significantly contribute to their affective commitment to the organization. More recently, a meta-analysis by (28) explored the impact of diversity and inclusion initiatives on organizational performance. The results showed that organizations that effectively implement inclusion programs experience increased innovation, better decision-making, and higher employee engagement and satisfaction. Furthermore, strong leadership support for DEI is associated with improved financial performance and competitive advantage. Based on the relationship between these two variables, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H₁: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the Inclusion Program in the Workplace and Organizational Commitment.

F. The Relationship between Workplace Inclusion Programs and Employee Productivity (ASN)

Starting from research conducted by (29), this study explores how inclusive leadership can increase employee work engagement, which in turn increases productivity. This study highlights the importance of the role of leaders in creating an inclusive environment that motivates employees to work more efficiently. In line with this, (30) in their study stated the effectiveness of diversity training in creating an inclusive work environment and its impact on employee productivity. The results of the study indicate that effective training can increase employee engagement and performance. In contrast, (28) presented research results stating that this meta-analysis reviews the impact of diversity and inclusion initiatives on organizational performance. The findings indicate that effective inclusion programs improve employee innovation, decision-making, and productivity, especially with strong leadership support. Furthermore, (31) concluded that workforce diversity, when properly managed through inclusion programs, can improve employee productivity. This study emphasizes the importance of effective management in creating an inclusive work environment. Based on the relationship between these two variables, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H₂: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the Inclusion Program in the Workplace and Employee Productivity.

G. The Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Employee Productivity

Based on research conducted by (32), researchers examined how organizational culture influences employee commitment and its impact on productivity. This study showed that high organizational commitment can significantly improve employee performance. Furthermore, (33) examined how organizational climate influences organizational commitment and perceived performance in the context of a general hospital. The results showed a positive relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance. In contrast, (34) explored the relationship between employee commitment and organizational productivity, finding that higher commitment was significantly associated with higher productivity. Based on the relationship between these two variables, the following hypotheses can be formulated.

H₃: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between Organizational Commitment and Employee Productivity.

H. Organizational Commitment Mediates the Relationship between Workplace Inclusion Programs and Employee Productivity

Based on several studies that raise several issues relevant to the mediation of organizational commitment in the relationship between workplace inclusion programs and employee productivity. Some of these studies include (29). This study explores how inclusive leadership can increase employee work engagement, which in turn increases productivity. This study also highlights the role of organizational commitment as a mediator in this relationship. Furthermore, (7) this study reviews various models of inclusion in the workplace and how inclusion programs can increase organizational commitment and employee productivity. This article also discusses the mediation of organizational commitment in the relationship between inclusion and productivity. A different point is conveyed by (27) this study examines how employee perceptions of diversity and inclusion approaches in the organization affect their behavior, including productivity, through the mediation of organizational commitment. Furthermore, research conducted by (35) explored how perceived organizational support can influence employee creativity, with organizational commitment as a mediator. Although focused on creativity, these findings are relevant to understanding productivity dynamics. Based on the relationship between these three variables, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H₄: It is suspected that Organizational Commitment can mediate the relationship between Workplace Inclusion Programs and Employee Productivity.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

This research is a descriptive quantitative study with an explanatory research approach. It uses previous issues on the effectiveness of inclusion programs, ASN work productivity, and organizational commitment as a springboard to identify unique elements within each topic and combine them into new and distinct elements.

B. Population and Research Sample

The population in this study is all State Civil Apparatus (ASN) with both structural and functional ranks in Ponorogo Regency. According to statistical data at <https://ponorogokab.bps.go.id/>, the number of ASN in Ponorogo Regency, by position, both functional and structural, is 8,990 employees, spread across 60 Regional Government Agencies (SKPD).

A sample is a portion of a population selected through a specific method in a clear and detailed manner (36). The sampling technique in this study used a purposive sampling method, selecting subjects from each Regional Work Unit (SKPD) proportionally and in a balanced manner (37). The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula. From the existing population, calculations using the Slovin formula at a tolerance level of 10% resulted in a sample size of 99 State Civil Apparatus (ASN). The collected data were then analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with the help of SmartPLS software.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive Analysis

Based on the results of the questionnaire by the State Civil Apparatus in Ponorogo Regency, the following description of respondents was obtained.

Table 1. Respondent Description

	<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender	<i>Male</i>	38	38,38%
	<i>Female</i>	61	61,62%
	Total	99	100%
Age	<i>30 - 40</i>	43	43,43%
	<i>41 - 50</i>	45	45,45%
	<i>51 - 60</i>	11	11,11%
	Total	99	100%
Last education	<i>S-1</i>	58	58,59%
	<i>S-2</i>	41	41,41%
	Total	99	100%
Length of work	<i>10 - 15</i>	46	46,46%
	<i>16 - 20</i>	41	41,41%
	<i>21 - 25</i>	12	12,12%
	Total	99	100%

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2025

The composition of respondents in this study demonstrates the significant diversity within the Ponorogo Regency civil servant (ASN) environment, providing an important basis for analyzing the effectiveness of inclusion programs. The majority of respondents were women (61.62%), reflecting the increasingly strong role of women in competencies, which demands inclusion policies that guarantee equal opportunities for all employees. In terms of age, most respondents were between 30 and 50 years old (88.88%), a highly productive career phase that requires a supportive, fair, and nurturing work environment to maintain motivation and productivity. The high level of education of respondents, with 58.59% having a bachelor's degree and 41.41% having a master's degree, reflects a strong intellectual capacity, which in turn fosters higher expectations for transparency, fairness, participation, and tangible inclusion practices in the workplace. In addition, the majority of respondents have a working period of 10–20 years (87.87%), indicating that they have long interacted with the bureaucratic system and have a deep understanding of organizational dynamics, so their perception of inclusion is very representative in assessing the extent to which the program is truly felt and influences commitment and productivity. Thus, this demographic structure shows that the diversity of Ponorogo employees is not only an objective condition, but also a strategic context that makes the urgency of implementing inclusion programs increasingly relevant and decisive for the creation of a regional bureaucracy that is highly committed and capable of optimal performance.

B. Data Quality Test Results

1. Normality

Table 2. Normality test results

Name	Excess kurtosis	Skewness
X.1	-0.804	-0.063
X.2	-0.427	-0.267
X.3	-0.289	-0.273
X.4	-0.544	-0.314
X.5	-0.860	-0.111
X.6	-0.465	-0.156
X.7	-0.772	-0.189
Y1.1	-1.113	0.069
Y1.2	-0.536	-0.241
Y1.3	-0.488	-0.238
Y1.4	-0.824	-0.174
Y1.5	-0.693	-0.220
Y2.1	-0.551	-0.391
Y2.2	-0.182	-0.492
Y2.3	-0.793	-0.246
Y2.4	-0.686	-0.351
Y2.5	-0.514	-0.345
Y2.6	-0.840	-0.311

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Data normality was tested using skewness and excess kurtosis values, with the provision that the data is considered normally distributed if the skewness and kurtosis values are in the range of -2 to 2. Based on the analysis results, all indicators in the model have skewness and kurtosis values that are within this range, so it can be concluded that the data meets the assumption of normality. The skewness values for all indicators range from -0.492 to 0.069, which indicates that the data distribution has no extreme skew to the left or right. Meanwhile, the excess kurtosis value ranges from -1.113 to -0.182, which indicates that the data distribution is not too sharp or too flat compared to a normal distribution. In addition, the variables RX, RY₁, and RY₂ have excess kurtosis and skewness values of 0.000, which indicates a balanced distribution. Thus, the assumption of normality in this study is met, so the data can be used for further analysis without the need for additional transformation.

2. Outer Model

a. Convergent Validity

1) Outer Loading

Table 3. Outer Loading result

Connection	Outer loadings
X. ₁ <- X.Inclusion	0,865
X. ₂ <- X.Inclusion	0,860
X. ₃ <- X.Inclusion	0,851
X. ₄ <- X.Inclusion	0,868
X. ₅ <- X.Inclusion	0,913
X. ₆ <- X.Inclusion	0,845
X. ₇ <- X.Inclusion	0,900
Y _{1.1} <- Y ₁ .Commitment	0,851
Y _{1.2} <- Y ₁ .Commitment	0,874
Y _{1.3} <- Y ₁ .Commitment	0,875
Y _{1.4} <- Y ₁ .Commitment	0,888
Y _{1.5} <- Y ₁ .Commitment	0,881
Y _{2.1} <- Y ₂ .Productivity	0,884
Y _{2.2} <- Y ₂ .Productivity	0,868
Y _{2.3} <- Y ₂ .Productivity	0,877
Y _{2.4} <- Y ₂ .Productivity	0,864
Y _{2.5} <- Y ₂ .Productivity	0,865
Y _{2.6} <- Y ₂ .Productivity	0,875

The results of the outer loading analysis show that all indicators have values above 0.7, which is the minimum limit to ensure convergent validity in the measurement model. The highest outer loading value is found in indicator X.₅ with

a value of 0.913, while the lowest value is found in indicator X.₆ with a value of 0.845. In the Y₁.Commitment construct, the outer loading values range from 0.851 to 0.888, while in the Y₂.Productivity construct, the values range from 0.864 to 0.884. Since all outer loading values have met the requirements above 0.7, it can be concluded that each indicator has a strong contribution to its respective construct, so that the convergent validity in this model has been met.

2) AVE

Table 4. AVE result

Variable	Average variance extracted (AVE)
X.Inclusion	0,760
Y ₁ .Commitment	0,764
Y ₂ .Productivity	0,761

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is used to measure convergent validity, with the provision that the AVE value must be more than 0.5 so that the construct can be said to have a good level of validity. Based on the analysis results, the variable X. Inclusion has an AVE value of 0.760, the variable Y₁. Commitment is 0.764, and the variable Y₂. Productivity is 0.761. All AVE values are above the minimum limit of 0.5, which indicates that each construct is able to explain more than 50% of the variance of its indicators. Thus, the convergent validity in this model has been met, which means that each latent variable can represent its indicators well.

b. Discriminant Validity

Table 5. Discriminant Validity result

Connection	Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)
Y ₁ .Commitment <-> X.Inclusion	0,823
Y ₂ .Productivity <-> X.Inclusion	0,665
Y ₂ .Productivity <-> Y ₁ .Commitment	0,674

Discriminant validity was tested using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) value, with the stipulation that the HTMT

value must be below 0.90 so that it can be said that each construct in this model has good discriminant validity. Based on the analysis results, the HTMT value for the relationship between Y₁.Commitment and X.Inclusion is 0.823, the relationship between Y₂.Productivity and X.Inclusion is 0.665, and the relationship between Y₂.Productivity and Y₁.Commitment is 0.674. All HTMT values in the table are below the maximum limit of 0.90, which indicates that each construct has a clear difference from each other and there is no multicollinearity problem between constructs. Thus, the discriminant validity in this model has been met, so that each latent variable can be considered to represent a significantly different concept.

c. Reliability

Table 6. Reliability result

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)
X.Inclusion	0,947	0,948	0,957
Y1.Commitment	0,923	0,923	0,942
Y2.Productivity	0,937	0,938	0,950

The reliability test in this model was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (rho_a), and Composite Reliability (rho_c), with the provision that a good reliability value must be more than 0.7 to indicate high internal consistency. Based on the analysis results, the variable X. Inclusion has a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.947, rho_a of 0.948, and rho_c of 0.957. The variable Y₁. Commitment has a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.923, rho_a of 0.923, and rho_c of 0.942. Meanwhile, the variable Y₂. Productivity has a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.937, rho_a of 0.938, and rho_c of 0.950. All three variables' reliability values were well above the minimum threshold of 0.7, indicating that this research instrument has excellent internal consistency. Therefore, it can be concluded that all constructs in the model have high reliability and can be used for consistent measurement.

3. INNER MODEL

a. VIF

Table 7. VIF Result

Connection	VIF
X.Inclusion -> Y ₁ .Commitment	1,000
X.Inclusion -> Y ₂ .Productivity	2,466
Y ₁ .Commitment -> Y ₂ .Productivity	2,466

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test is used to detect multicollinearity in the structural model, with the provision that the VIF value must be less than 5 to avoid serious multicollinearity problems. Based on the analysis results, the VIF value for the relationship between X.Inclusion and Y₁.Commitment is 1.000, while for the relationship between X.Inclusion and Y₂.Productivity and the relationship between Y₁.Commitment and Y₂.Productivity each has a VIF value of 2.466. All VIF values are below the threshold of 5, which indicates that there is no multicollinearity problem in this model. Thus, the model can be said to be stable, and the independent variables used do not have excessive linear relationships with each other, so that the regression analysis in this model can be carried out well.

b. R-Square

Table 8. R-Square Result

Variable	R-square
Y ₁ .Commitment	0,594
Y ₂ .Productivity	0,446

The R-square value is used to measure how much the independent variables are able to explain the dependent variable in the structural model, with the provision that the higher the R-square value, the better the predictive ability of the model. Based on the analysis results, the variable Y₁.Commitment has an R-square value of 0.594, which means that 59.4% of the variance in Y₁.Commitment can be explained by the variable X.Inclusion, while the rest is influenced by other factors outside the model. Meanwhile, the variable Y₂.Productivity has an R-square value of 0.446, which indicates that 44.6% of the variance in Y₂.Productivity can be explained by the variables X.Inclusion and Y₁.Commitment. In general, an R-square value above 0.5 indicates a fairly good predictive power of the model, although the value of

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0.446 for Y₂.Productivity is in the medium category. Thus, this model has a fairly good ability to explain the relationship between latent variables, although there are still other factors that can contribute to the variance of the dependent variable.

c. F-Square

Table 9. F-Square Result

Connection	f-square
X. Inclusion -> Y1. Commitment	1,466
X. Inclusion -> Y2. Productivity	0,091
Y1. Commitment -> Y2. Productivity	0,093

The f-square value is used to measure the effect size of the independent variable on the dependent variable in the structural model, with the provision that an f-square value of 0.02 indicates a small effect, 0.15 indicates a medium effect, and 0.35 or more indicates a large effect. Based on the results of the analysis, the relationship between X.Inclusion and Y₁.Commitment has an f-square value of 1.466, which indicates that X.Inclusion has a very large influence on Y₁.Commitment. Meanwhile, the relationship between X.Inclusion and Y₂.Productivity has an f-square value of 0.091, which indicates that its influence on Y₂.Productivity is relatively small. Likewise, the relationship between Y₁.Commitment and Y₂.Productivity has an f-square value of 0.093, which also indicates a small influence. Thus, it can be concluded that X.Inclusion has a very strong impact on Y₁.Commitment, but its influence on Y₂.Productivity is relatively small, as is the influence of Y₁.Commitment on Y₂.Productivity. This indicates that there are other factors outside the model that may have a greater contribution to the variable Y₂.Productivity.

4. FIT MODELS

Table 10. FIT Result

Indicator	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0,045	0,045

Model fit in SmartPLS analysis was evaluated using the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), with the requirement that the SRMR value must be below 0.08 for the model to be considered a good fit with the data. Based on the

analysis results, the SRMR value for the saturated and estimated models was 0.045, which is well below the maximum limit of 0.08. This indicates that the tested model has a very good level of fit with the observed data, so that the difference between the observed and predicted covariance matrices by the model is quite small. Thus, it can be concluded that the model used in this study has a good fit and is reliable in explaining the relationship between latent variables.

5. Structural Equation Model Test Results

Picture 1. Structural Equation Model Test Results

6. Hypothesis Testing Results

a. Direct Influence

Table 11. Direct Influence Result

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
X. Inclusion-> Y1. Commitment	0,771	17,168	0,000
X. Inclusion-> Y2. Produktivitas	0,352	2,705	0,007
Y1. Commitment-> Y2. Produktivitas	0,357	2,697	0,007

The direct influence in the structural model is evaluated based on the Original Sample (O), T-Statistics, and P-Values, with the provision that the T-Statistics value must be more than 1.96 and P-Values must be less than 0.05 for the relationship between variables to be significant. Based on the results of the analysis, the relationship between X.Inclusion and Y₁.Commitment has an influence coefficient of 0.771 with a T-Statistics of 17.168 and P-Values of 0.000, which indicates a very strong and significant positive influence. The relationship between X.Inclusion and Y₂.Productivity has an influence coefficient of 0.352 with a T-Statistics of 2.705 and P-Values of 0.007, which also indicates a positive and significant influence.

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Meanwhile, the relationship between Y_1 .Commitment and Y_2 .Productivity has an influence coefficient of 0.357 with a T-Statistic of 2.697 and a P-Value of 0.007, which means its influence is also significant. Thus, all relationships in this model are proven to be significant, which indicates that X.Inclusion plays an important role in increasing Y_1 .Commitment and Y_2 .Productivity, and Y_1 .Commitment also contributes positively to Y_2 .Productivity.

b. The Effect Of Mediation

Table 12. Effect Of Mediation Result

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
X. Inclusion-> Y_2 .Produktivitas	0,352	2,705	0,007

The mediation effect in the structural model was analyzed to determine whether the mediating variable plays a role in the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The conditions used are that the T-Statistics value must be more than 1.96 and P-Values must be less than 0.05 for the mediation effect to be significant. Based on the analysis results, the indirect effect of X.Inclusion on Y_2 .Productivity through the mediation variable Y_1 .Commitment has an influence coefficient of 0.276 with a T-Statistics of 2.557 and P-Values of 0.011. This value indicates that the mediation effect is significant, which means that Y_1 .Commitment plays a role in strengthening the relationship between X.Inclusion and Y_2 .Productivity. Thus, in addition to having a direct effect on Y_2 .Productivity, X.Inclusion also has an indirect effect through Y_1 .Commitment, which shows that increasing inclusion has an important role in increasing productivity by strengthening commitment first.

V. DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that inclusion programs are a dominant factor in shaping civil servants' organizational commitment. This strong relationship is consistent with international literature, which emphasizes that employees demonstrate higher levels of commitment when they feel cared for, valued, and given space to develop (2) and (27). The very large effect size reinforces the assertion that inclusion is a crucial foundation for building employees' emotional bonds with the organization.

The influence of inclusion programs on civil servant productivity was also proven significant. Although the effect size was not as large as the effect on commitment, these

results align with research (29), which confirms that an inclusive work environment increases employee engagement and focus on their tasks.

Furthermore, organizational commitment has been shown to be an important predictor of productivity. Employees who feel emotionally attached to their organization tend to demonstrate a higher work ethic and stability in carrying out their duties. The significant mediation effect indicates that inclusion builds commitment, and this commitment ultimately increases productivity. In other words, civil servant productivity depends not only on formal policies, but also on how civil servants feel valued throughout the work process.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study confirms that workplace inclusion programs are an effective strategy for increasing civil servant productivity in Ponorogo Regency. Organizational commitment acts as a psychological bridge that strengthens this influence. Therefore, local governments need to expand the implementation of inclusion programs, ensure equal access to opportunities, and build a work culture that values diversity.

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